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DESIGN THINKING – THE WAY TO TEACH DESIGN IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION

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Introduction - Why is the session relevant?

Innovation is the engine of industry, and it can also make a better world. **Design Thinking** is a methodology that is fast becoming a mainstay in business strategy all around the world. Centered on creativity, empathy, and putting the user's needs as the heart of the problem, Design Thinking is seen as an important tool for driving innovation and sustained business growth. As the "business of innovation" becomes increasingly important to strategic decision makers in all sectors and industries, it is necessary for design thinking to become ingrained in the engineer's mindset. Design thinking culture must be integrated across the engineering curriculum beyond the capstone design experience.

What are session participants expected to learn?

Engineering professors need to understand how traditional design differs from the design thinking approach in order to integrate this design method into the curriculum. At the end of this 90-hour workshop participants will have:

- 1) learned about design thinking, its history and implementation;
- 2) reflect on the design thinking implementation steps, and
- 3) brainstorm ways to infuse design thinking in the engineering curriculum.

How are session participants motivated?

In order to achieve desired learning outcomes, the workshop will be conducted utilizing a series of short presentations followed by exercises and design challenges, reflections and brainstorming done by participants in groups of 2 or 3 (like Think-Pair-Share). Due to the time limitations, one or two groups of participants will be asked to share their discussions/designs/reflections.

How will results be summarized?

Participants take home:

- 1) what is design thinking and why it is important in the 21st Century, and,
- 2) consider various ways to implement the design thinking method into the curriculum.

How is this work significant for Engineering Education?

This design approach is behind the success of Silicon Valley and other regional innovation hubs around the world. As the "business of innovation" becomes increasingly important to strategic decision makers in all sectors and industries in the 21st Century, and as the world increases to rely on green engineering for sustainability, it is necessary for design thinking to become ingrained in the engineer's mindset. Therefore, the design thinking culture must be integrated across the engineering curriculum beyond the capstone design experience, so that this approach (human centered design) is engrained in the engineer's mind. This workshop is designed for STEM deans and professors who wish to learn about design thinking and how to integrate it in the curriculum and is meant to give participants a full cycle through the design-thinking process in as short time as possible.

Workshop Agenda

Design Challenge 1 (activity)	10 minutes
What is Design Thinking and Why is it Important in the 21 st Century?	20 minutes
What are the Design Thinking Steps?	10 minutes
Design Challenge 2 (activity)	10 minutes
Ways to Integrate Design Thinking into the Curricula	20 minutes
Brainstorming (activity)	10 minutes
Final Thoughts and Workshop Evaluation	10 minutes